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CONDITIONAL RANDOM FIELD PREDICTION MODEL FOR SEGMENTING BREAST MASSES FROM DIGITAL MAMMOGRAMS

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Abstract. The segmentation of masses from mammograms is a difficult challenge due to their variety in shape, appearance, and size, as well as their low signal-to-noise ratio..

Key words: segmentation, CRF, prediction model, mammogram, computer-aided diagnosis systems

Assume that we have an annotated dataset D including images of the region of interest (ROI) of the mass, represented by $x: \Omega \rightarrow R(\Omega \in R^2)$, and the respectively manually provided segmentation mask $y: \Omega \rightarrow \{-1,+1\}$, where $D=(x, y)_{i=1}^{|D|}$. Also assume that the parameter of our structured output prediction model is denoted by θ and the graph $G = (V, E)$ links the image x and labels y , where V is the set of graph nodes and E , the set of graph edges. The process of learning the parameter of structured prediction mode is done through the minimization of the following empirical loss function:

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{|D|} \sum_{i=1}^{|D|} l(x_i, y_i, \theta), \quad (1)$$

here $l(x, y, \theta)$ is a continuous and convex loss function being minimized that defines the structured model. We use CRF formulation for solving (1). In particular, the CRF formulation uses the loss:

$$l(x_i, y_i, \theta) = A(x_i, \theta) - E(y_i, x_i; \theta), \quad (2)$$

here $A(x, \theta) = \log \sum_{y \in \{-1,+1\}^{|\Omega| \times |\Omega|}} \exp\{E(y, x; \theta)\}$ is the log-partition

function that ensures normalization, and

$$E(y, x; \theta) = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i \in V} \theta_{1,k} \psi^{(1,k)}(y(i), x) + \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i,j \in E} \theta_{2,k} \psi^{(2,k)}(y(i), y(j), x), \quad (3)$$

In(3) $\psi^{(1,k)}(.,.)$ denotes one of the K potential functions between label and pixel nodes, $\psi^{(2,k)}(.,.)$ representing one of the L potential functions on the edges between label nodes, $\theta = [\theta_{1,1}, \dots, \theta_{1,K}, \dots, \theta_{2,L}]^T \in R^{K+L}$, and $y(i)$ being the i^{th} component of vector y .

Conditional Random Field. The solution of (1) using the CRF loss function in (2) involves the computation of the log-partition function $A(x, \theta)$. The tree re-weighted belief propagation algorithm provides the following upper bound to this log-partition function:

$$A(x, \theta) = \max_{\mu \in M} \theta^t \mu + H(\mu), \quad (4)$$

here $M = \{\mu: \exists \theta, \mu = \mu\}$ denotes the marginal polytope, $\mu = \sum_{y \in \{-1,+1\}^{|\Omega| \times |\Omega|}} P(y|x, \theta) f(y)$, with $f(y)$ denoting the set of indicator functions of possible configurations of each clique and variable in the graph(as denoted in(3)), $P(y|x, \theta) = \exp\{E(y, x; \theta) - A(x, \theta)\}$ indicating the conditional probability of the annotation y given the image x and parameters θ (where we assume that this conditional probability function belongs to the exponential family), and $H(\mu) = -\sum_{y \in \{-1,+1\}^{|\Omega| \times |\Omega|}} P(y|x, \theta) \log P(y|x, \theta)$ is the entropy.

It is important to note that for general graphs with cycles (as in this study), the marginal polytope M is difficult to describe and the entropy $H(\mu)$ is not tractable. TRW addresses these concerns by first replacing the marginal polytope with a superset $L \supset M$ that only accounts for the marginals local constraints, and then approximating the entropy calculation with an upper bound. Specifically,

$$L = \{\mu: \sum_{y(c|y(i))} \mu(y(c)) = \mu(y(i)), \sum_{y(i)} \mu(y(i)) = 1\}, \quad (5)$$

replaces M in (5) and represents the local polytope (with $\mu(y(i)) = \sum_{\acute{y}} P(\acute{y}|x, \theta) \delta(\acute{y}(i) - y(i))$ and $\delta(.)$ is the Dirac delta function), c indexes a graph clique, and the entropy approximation(that replaces $H(\mu)$ in (5) is defined by)

$$\tilde{H}(\mu) = \sum_{y(i)} H(\mu(y(i))) - \sum_{y(c)} I(\mu(y(c))), \quad (6)$$

where $H(\mu(y(i))) = -\sum_{s(i)} \mu(y(i)) \log \mu(y(i))$ is the univariate entropy of

variable $y(i)$, $I(\mu(y(c))) = \sum_{y(c)} \mu(y(i)) \log \frac{\mu(y(c))}{\prod_{i \in c} \mu(y(i))}$ is the mutual information of the cliques in our model, and ρ_c is a free parameter providing the upper bound on the entropy. Therefore, the estimation of $A(x; \theta)$ and associated marginal in (5) is based on the following message-passing updates:

$$m_c \propto \sum_{y(c) \setminus y(i)} \exp \left\{ \frac{1}{\rho_c} \psi_c(y(i), y(j); \theta) \right\} \prod_{j \in c \setminus i} \exp \left\{ \frac{1}{\rho_c} \psi_i(y(i), x; \theta) \right\} \frac{\prod_{d; j \in d} m_d(s(j))^{\rho_d}}{m_c(s(j))} \quad (7)$$

where $\phi_i(y(i), x; \theta) = \sum_{k=1}^K w_{1,k} \psi^{(1,k)}(y(i), x)$ and $\psi_c(y(i), y(j); \theta) = \sum_{l=1}^L w_{2,k} \psi^{(2,k)}(y(i), y(j), x)$. When the message-passing algorithm converges, the beliefs for the associated marginals are expressed as follows:

$$\mu_c(y(c)) \propto \frac{1}{\rho_c} \psi_c(y(i), y(j)) \prod_{i \in c} \psi_i(y(i), x; \theta) \frac{\prod_{d; j \in d} m_d(y(j))^{\rho_d}}{m_c(y(i))} \mu_i(y_i) \propto \exp(\psi_i(y(i), x; \theta)) \prod_{d; i \in d} m_d(y(i))^{\rho_d}, \quad (8)$$

The learning process involved in the assessment of θ is typically based on gradient descent that minimizes the loss in (2) and should run until convergence, which is characterized by the change rate of θ between successive gradient descent iterations.

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